

Assessing Biochar Capacity To Reduce Organophosphorus Pesticide Bioavailability

Snežana Maletić^{a*}, Jelena Beljin^a, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski^a, Peng Zhang^{b,c},
Hongwen Sun^{b,c}, Srđan Rončević^a

^a University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

^b MOE Key Laboratory of Pollution Processes and Environmental Criteria, College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Nankai University, Tianjin 300350, China

^c Tianjin Engineering Center of Environmental Diagnosis and Contamination Remediation, Tianjin 300350, China

* Corresponding author. E-mail: snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs

As one of the most used classes of pesticides, organophosphorus pesticides (OPPs) amount to 38% of the total world market, mainly due to their high performance, broadspectrum insecticidal activity, chemical stability, high efficiency, and low cost (Dash and Osborne, 2020). Despite these benefits, the persistence, mobility, and toxicity of OPPs in the environment seriously threaten groundwater, the largest body of fresh water and the most important drinking water resource. OPPs act as neurotoxins, by inhibiting proper enzyme activity in the central nervous system (Soares et al., 2021) and potentially causing severe neurotoxicity and cognitive impairments. Their fate in sediment is mainly controlled by sorption and biodegradation as these two processes govern their mobility and overall behavior (Kragulj Isakovski et al., 2020). The main objective of this research was to investigate: (1) the biosorption and biodegradation potential of five selected OPPs (fenthion, fenitrothion, parathion methyl, malathion, and disulfoton) in the alluvial sediment of the Danube river, (2) the impact of carbon rich materials amendment such as hydrochar and biochar on sorption and biodegradation potential of OPPs, and (3) to colonise the hydrochar and biochar with OPPs degrading bacteria isolated from the contaminated sediment to improve their potential for biodegradation. The biodegradation and biosorption of OPPs were tested in batch experiments by adding the bacterial strain *Bacillus megaterium* BD5 in a mineral medium. Results indicated that *Bacillus megaterium* BD5 efficiently biodegraded fenitrothion, malathion, and parathion methyl in batch experiments in mineral medium, while abiotic degradation was the predominant mode of removal for disulfoton and fenthion ($p < 0.05$). Next, batch experiments with sediment amended with biochars and hydrochars of sugar beet shreds and *Miscanthus × giganteus* with and without bacterial biofilm were conducted. The influence of biostimulation was also tested by the addition of nutrients. Results indicated that the OPPs addition of amendments caused OPPs longer persistence in sediments ($p < 0.05$). While the addition of amendments colonised with BD strains efficiently degraded all investigated OPPs ($p < 0.05$).

Keywords: Organophosphorus pesticides, biodegradation, biosorption, biochar, hydrochar

Acknowledgements: Funded by EU grant #101059546-TwinSubDyn and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Serbia-China Mobility Projects 2024-2026)

1. Kragulj Isakovski, M., Maletić, S., Tamindžija, D., Apostolović, T., Petrović, J., Tričković, J., Agbaba, J. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111156>
2. Soares, P.R.S., Birolli, W.G., Ferreira, I.M., Porto, A.L.M.: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112185>
3. Dash, D.M. and Osborne, W.J.: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.110290>